

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY MODULE VI

DRIVING INNOVATION IN THE COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY THROUGH USER STORIES: INTEROPERABILITY AND DATA GOVERNANCE

Highlights Report

Introduction

One of the elements required to achieve an attractive and competitive agricultural sector supporting environmental and sustainability goals is the need to build public policies founded upon data rigor. Simplification, modernisation, cost-effectiveness, and accountability are essential components to ensure compliance with existing European Commission practices, as well as the use of data repositories, data sharing regulations, and data governance for the current or new CAP programming periods.

But this context necessitates continuous innovation. Various initiatives are being developed at the European level to reinforce the role of data and its governance in CAP implementation, thereby facilitating evidence-based decision-making.

ORGANISER:

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Main highlights from the module

This highlight report focuses [on the sixth module](#) of the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), led by the European Association for Innovation in Local Development ([AEIDL](#)), which took place on November 5th, 2025, completing the third delivery dedicated to [technical protocols and methodological guidelines](#) this year. This module is the result of work undertaken by [NEUROPUBLIC](#), [ABACO](#) and [ITACyL](#), which is detailed in the high-level technical document [Methodological guidelines and technical protocols on data integration](#).

During the session, practical methodological guidance was offered, went beyond explaining the "what" of these protocols, and presenting digital tools **using a user-story approach to bridge the gap between high-level policy and effective implementation**. This approach effectively translates technical and scientific findings into practical guidance that Member States can adopt or adapt, helping policymakers, CAP Managing Authorities, and agricultural stakeholders to:

- Improve CAP SP monitoring by leveraging farm-level and landscape-level data.
- Enhance compliance verification and performance monitoring using advanced data sources (e.g., FSDN).
- Support environmental and sustainability goals, including biodiversity conservation, soil health management, and pesticide usage reduction, all aligned with the Green Deal targets.

However, **how do these advancements materialise, and how can we exemplify the outcomes of rigorous information control in real-life scenarios?** To illustrate this transition, this report includes three practical examples of user stories presented during the Module as a methodological application, extracted from [the case studies developed in Spain, Italy, and Greece](#) within the Tools4CAP project, thereby demonstrating the potential of implementing these tools on the ground.

This module forms part of the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), which aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer – learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet the end users' needs. [Tools4CAP](#), coordinated by [ECORYS](#), is a project embedded in Horizon Programme that involves 21 partner organisations from 18 EU countries with outstanding expertise in economic, environmental, climate and social issues, new data sources and monitoring technologies, as well as in stakeholder engagement, social, environmental, and animal welfare-related data and indicators, in agricultural and rural development contexts.

Setting the technical foundation: requirements for landscape monitoring

Christian Schingo

ABACO Group

To achieve the policy objectives and reinforce the role of data and its governance in CAP implementation, it is necessary to **establish a clear, interconnected technical foundation to develop protocols and methodological guidelines for evidence-based policymaking**. During the introduction, **Christian Schingo (ABACO)**, presented the three main pillars and key lessons learned from this process on integrated data and digital tools.

Pillar 1: interoperability and legal compliance

Effective landscape monitoring is fundamentally reliant on robust interoperability. This involves stressing the need for standardised data exchanges and a harmonised spatial infrastructure across all Member States. The system must ensure full legal compliance with established European frameworks, including the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR), the [Data Governance Act](#), and the [INSPIRE Directive](#). Establishing these requirements ensures that the data can be exchanged and utilised lawfully and without friction.

Lesson learned: Interoperability between statistical and administrative databases seems rare, but when achieved, it significantly reduces the data collection burden. On the other side, when data acquired on-farm are used out of the farm, data sharing challenges such as privacy and ownership arise (GDPR), whilst accessibility issues and a lack of standard data models become the main challenges for off-farm data integration.

Pillar 2: the role of the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN)

The [Farm Sustainability Data Network \(FSDN\)](#) represents a significant step towards achieving harmonised, high-quality farm-level sustainability data, which central role is to **improve the monitoring of CAP sustainability goals by providing granular and comparable data necessary for performance evaluation and policy adjustment**. Without this standardised, ground-level information, holistic sustainability assessment remains challenging.

Lesson learned: New data acquisition technologies at farm level, which are integrated into regular farm operations, could be widely utilised for CSP monitoring and evaluation. However, the social-economic aspects of the CAP remain the most challenging ones to assess with current technologies at the farm level.

Pillar 3: integrated data at farm and landscape level

The effectiveness of the monitoring tool depends upon the successful integration of farm-level and landscape-level data. The approach mandates the merging of highly diverse data sources, including information from Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS), data gathered via Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, Earth Observation (EO) imagery (specifically from Copernicus), administrative systems, and various national and EU datasets. Only through this comprehensive integration can policymakers achieve the necessary spatial and temporal perspective for evidence-based decision-making.

Lesson learned: The fusion of diverse data sources is essential as it effectively compensates for the limitations and gaps inherent in individual technology applications. Only through this comprehensive integration policymakers can achieve the necessary spatial and temporal perspective for evidence-based decision-making.

Understanding and implementing user stories: interoperability challenges and initiatives for data governance

Giorgos Charvalis

NEUROPUBLIC

Before introducing the user stories, it is important to understand that CAP policy tasks included in this module and the aim of its technical protocols are to **evaluate the impact of CAP strategic plan interventions and to help design (or redesign) future interventions** for the next programming period.

To do this properly, it is needed more than just farm-level

data and broader sources—like those in the [Landscape Monitoring Framework](#). To deliver useful insights, all this information needs to be **combined with data reported through administrative databases** which require advanced data analysis methods and models. In this context, digital tools can offer valuable support for ex-ante analysis in CAP Strategic Plan design, especially for setting interventions and targets.

Framework for CSP design and monitoring

To apply the user story approach coherently in this context, two main concepts must be clarified.

Firstly, is **interoperability**, referring to the technical ability of different information systems, or components to work together automatically and exchange data in standardised formats. It acts as a shared digital language, allowing systems—from [Earth Observation \(EO\)](#) platform and farm sensors to administrative database like [Integrated Administration and Control System](#) or [Farm Sustainability Data Network](#)— to communicate and integrate data effectively, and understand each other's data and work together. This **prevents data from being isolated in separate systems, or "silos"** and establishes the technical protocols necessary to effectively merge and analyse different types of data.

Despite this necessity, achieving full interoperability faces [significant challenges across four main levels](#):

- 1. Technical complexity:** systems differ in technologies, formats, and interfaces, making real-time integration difficult.
- 2. Syntactic interoperability:** usually associated with data formats and encodings (e.g. XML, JSON and RDF).
- 3. Semantic ambiguity:** terms like “farm” or “land use” may have different meanings across databases or Member States, affecting policy reliability.
- 4. Governance and legal burdens:** challenges related to data ownership, access rights, and strict regulatory compliance—particularly under GDPR—must be overcome to ensure data is shared securely and legally across organisational boundaries.

Ensuring data exchange requires strict alignment with EU regulatory frameworks such as the [INSPIRE Directive](#) and the [Open Data Directive](#), along with adherence to the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Secondly, a technical but nonetheless high-level tool is required, **Unified Modelling Language**, which is a standardised visual language used to represent the structure and behaviour of software systems. In the context of CAP monitoring tools, UML helps translate complex system interactions into intuitive diagrams that clarify how different actors (e.g. farmers, FMIS providers, policy evaluators) and components (e.g. databases, APIs) exchange information over time.

Previous CAP programming periods revealed persistent challenges such as lack of appropriate data sources, inaccessible or overly aggregated data, and restrictions on combining datasets.

Giorgos Charvalis, NEUROPUBLIC

A step-by-step flow of the UML Sequence Diagram

Specifically, UML sequence diagrams are used to illustrate the operational flow of user stories—short, goal-oriented narratives that capture the needs of end users such as CAP Managing Authorities or Paying Agencies. These diagrams support the early stages of system design by bridging technical requirements with policy objectives, ensuring that digital tools align with CAP Strategic Plan goals and regulatory frameworks.

User stories: defining the need

The methodological approach in this module and in this report are the user stories, **designed to bridge the gap between policy objectives and technical solutions**, and is defined on a structured and narrative way that **describes a specific need, challenge, or desired solution from the perspective of an end-user**. In this case, could be a farmer, a policymaker, or a technical operator.

The user stories follow a standard format: **"As a [user], I want to [goal], so that I can [reason/benefit]"**, and serve two critical functions. The first one is to **illustrate how the data and digital tools will be used in a real-world agricultural or policy scenario**; and on the other, because **they translate high-level policy questions into actionable, measurable functional requirements** for the software developers and technical teams.

How do we build a user story? The User Story must be concise and communicate three essential pieces of information to the end-user, serving as a bridge between policy objectives and technical implementation.

1. Identify the user and determine **"who"** will the tool or feature will 'serve'. This should be a specific stakeholder group related to the CAP, for example, a Managing Authority, paying agency or environmental policy analyst.
2. Define the goal and specify the action the user needs to perform. This is the **"what"** and must be measurable and directly related to a CAP intervention, data or digital tool.
3. Finally, state the benefit and explain the value or outcome of achieving the goal. This is the **"why"** and ties the technical feature back to the overall CAP SP objectives.

In the Tools4CAP project, this methodology led to the creation of [seven detailed User Stories](#), each acting as a protocol for how integrated tools will respond to key policy questions in the CAP Strategic Plans. These stories are strategically focused on the environmental and sustainability dimensions of the CAP, translating Green Deal ambitions into actionable digital requirements.

Soil Health

Using IoT sensors for monitoring soil conditions.

Pesticides

Integrating FMIS and Digital Farm Books for pesticide tracking.

Animal Welfare

Implementing Livestock Management Information Systems (LMIS).

Sustainable Food and Waste

Utilising blockchain for food traceability.

Irrigation and water

Integrating remote sensing, drought monitoring tools, and WEI+ analytics for CAP and SDG indicators.

Nutrients

Employing Variable Rate Technology (VRT) and FaST tools.

Landscape Features

Earth Observation-based monitoring of biodiversity and agroecological features.

The seven user stories developed by the project, each addressing a key CAP policy question

User story: pesticides and the Spanish case study

Alberto Gutiérrez

Agricultural Technological Institute of Castilla y Leon (ITACyL)

As part of the Tools4CAP project, the Spanish case study focused on integrating **farm-level data to monitor pesticide usage**, aligned with the [European Union's Green Deal objective of reducing both the risk and use of chemical pesticides](#). To support this goal, ITACyL applies the user story methodology to capture functional requirements for agile software development.

The study leverages Farm Management Information Systems, which support farmers in daily decision-making and collect granular data on agricultural practices. A key component is the Digital Farm Book, and the module within FMIS that records pesticide application at the field level. Once anonymised and aggregated, this data becomes a valuable input for agro-economic models, which help policymakers assess the impact of pesticide reduction strategies on crop yields and guide the design of CAP interventions.

Actors involved and their role

- Farmers, as they play a central role in this user story as they are expected to enter manually into the FMIS/Digital Farm Book information on the crop type, parcel/s and area treated, disease to control, type and dose of the product and the date-time of application.
- Advisor/ practitioner, as the application of pesticides needs to be prescribed by an authorised advisor to

ensure compliance with Integrated Pest Management standards.

- Digital technology expert: the different nature of the data sources, as well as the various technologies that are needed to estimate the actual impact of the CSP interventions, requires specialised personnel capable of managing APIs and interoperability standards.

Involved in data types

- Earth Observation data: the [Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem](#) is a service managed by the European Space Agency.
- European initiatives: JRC European Soil Data Center ([ESDAC](#)), Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey ([LUCAS](#)), EU Soil Observatory ([EUSO](#)), DG AGRI: Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN)/[Farm Sustainable Data Network](#) (FSDN), [Eurostat's sales of pesticides](#) dataset.
- Agriculture machinery data collected via different sensors provided in the agricultural machinery.
- Administrative data bases: [National Registry of Plant Protection Products](#) and [EU Pesticides Database](#).
- Public Registries: EU database of authorised Plant Protection Products (PPP), accessed via API to verify product compliance.

Step-by-step flow of the UML Sequence Diagram for the Spanish pesticide case study

The resulting user story

The User Story serves as the functional requirement for developers: *As a CAP Managing Authority, I want to access and cross-reference granular data from farmers' Digital Farm Books, so that I can monitor progress toward national pesticide reduction targets and evaluate the effectiveness of specific CAP interventions.*

The Spanish case study illustrates how digital innovation can support CAP Strategic Plans by transforming granular farm-level data into actionable insights. However, the transition from data collection to policy impact requires strategic alignment, institutional coordination, and regulatory clarity.

- One of the key challenges lies in **governance fragmentation**. While the Digital Farm Book defines the data to be collected related to pesticide use, the integration of these data into national and EU-level monitoring frameworks depends on coherent data flows across multiple actors: farmers, advisors, regional administrations, and EU institutions. This requires not only **technical interoperability but also institutional interoperability**.
- Lessons learned from the application of user stories in the case study highlights the need for **adaptive data**

governance. The current pesticide registration system often excludes minor crops due to limited commercial interest, creating blind spots in monitoring. Addressing this requires flexible mechanisms, such as incorporating exceptional authorisations or farmer-reported practices that reflect real-world usage and ensure representativeness.

- From a strategic perspective, the **Digital Farm Book can serve as a feedback loop within the CAP performance framework**, linking field-level practices to environmental indicators, to enable dynamic recalibration of interventions and supporting evidence-based decision-making. However, this potential is contingent on resolving usability barriers and ensuring that data collection does not become an additional bureaucratic burden for farmers.
- Finally, the Spanish experience underscores the **importance of stakeholder engagement**, such as farmer unions, agronomic experts, and digital service providers to be involved not only in data provision but also in system design and validation. **Their input is essential to ensure that digital tools are both technically robust and socially legitimate.**

User story: soil health and the Italian case study

Christian Schingo

ABACO Group

Christian Schingo, from ABACO, presented how this user story is being applied in the Italian case study through **the integration of field sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies that offers a transformative opportunity for monitoring soil health within the framework of CAP Strategic Plans**. Devices such as moisture sensors, nutrient monitors, and pH detectors provide real-time, high-resolution data that cannot be obtained through traditional sources. This enables more accurate, timely, and cost-effective monitoring of sustainability indicators.

By automating data collection and reducing reliance on manual inspections, IoT systems improve operational efficiency and allow for early detection of soil degradation, nutrient depletion, and water stress. When combined with Geographic Information Systems (GIS), these data streams offer a comprehensive spatial and temporal view of soil conditions across regions.

The technical architecture involves transmitting sensor data to gateway devices, preprocessing it for accuracy, and securely sharing it with CAP-authorized databases via APIs. **Policy evaluators can then access dashboards and reports to inform compliance assessments and strategic planning, while farmers receive tailored feedback through mobile applications or AIS platforms.**

This approach supports precision farming, enhances resource efficiency, and contributes to environmental goals such as reduced emissions and improved soil resilience. However, successful implementation requires agronomic expertise, robust data governance, and user-friendly systems to ensure adoption and policy relevance.

Actors involved and their role

- Farmers implement IoT devices on their land to monitor soil health.
- Technology provider/ expert: IoT system collects real-time soil data (e.g. moisture, pH, nutrients...) using sensors. Experts (e.g. licensed operators) are involved in installing and operating the hardware.
- Policymakers utilise data to evaluate and adapt Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans.

Involved in data types

- Sensor Data: Soil pH, Nutrient levels (N, P, K), Moisture content, Soil temperature, Organic matter concentration.
- Metadata: Location data (GPS coordinates), time stamps for data collection, crop type and farming practices.
- Environmental Data: Weather data (temperature, rainfall, humidity), irrigation and water usage records.
- Administrative Data: Farm boundaries and land-use patterns, CAP subsidy allocations, compliance data (e.g., adherence to CAP guidelines).

The resulting user story

In this case, the user story could be developed: *As a CAP Managing Authority, I want to access real-time soil health data collected through IoT sensors and integrated into*

administrative databases, so that I can evaluate compliance with soil-related CAP objectives and support evidence-based adjustments to strategic interventions.

This user story defines the need for **interoperable systems capable of ingesting granular, sensor-based data**, such as soil moisture, pH, organic matter, and translating it into actionable insights for CAP monitoring. It supports the calculation of key CAP indicators, including R.19PR (Improving and protecting soils) and I.11 (Enhancing carbon sequestration), by enabling continuous tracking of soil health parameters and their evolution over time.

Moreover, the integration of IoT data into CAP-authorized administrative systems aligns with the requirements of GAEC 5 (erosion prevention) and GAEC 6 (minimum soil cover), offering a robust mechanism for **verifying compliance with conditionality rules**. The secure transmission of data via APIs, using protocols such as HTTPS and token-based authentication, ensures adherence to EU data governance frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the INSPIRE Directive, and the Data Governance Act (DGA).

By embedding this functionality into CAP monitoring workflows, Managing Authorities can **move toward a more dynamic, data-driven evaluation model**—one that supports real-time feedback, regional benchmarking, and strategic recalibration of soil-related interventions.

Step-by-step flow of the UML Sequence Diagram for the Italian soil health case study

User story: irrigation and water management in Greek case study

Giorgos Charvalis

NEUROPUBLIC

Water scarcity and drought are increasing challenges across Europe, requiring sustainable irrigation and water management practices. This user story focuses on **integrating historical climate data, real-time meteorological inputs, drought indicators, and farm-level irrigation records** to monitor water usage. The aim is to support CAP Strategic Plans (CAP-SPs) in achieving sustainability goals, ensuring efficient resource allocation, and enhancing climate resilience in agriculture.

Actors involved and their role

- Farmers, to monitor and report irrigation practices including timing, volume, using FMIs tools, irrigation sensors, calendars, etc.
- FMIS providers, supplying the technology and platforms to record, process, and analyse the farmers irrigation data facilitation integration with external data sources.
- Water authorities and environmental agencies, to provide historical data on climate in multiple level, drought alerts, meteorological related variables.
- CAP policy makers, as end-users that monitor variables based on queries depending on LPIS data availability in a user interface. Use the output data to evaluate and adjust CAP SP and to ensure better water source allocation at a regional level.

Involved in data types

Environmental Data:

- Water usage and irrigation patterns from FMIS.
- Evapotranspiration (ET_0) estimates from EO data products (raster format) Evapotranspiration (ET_0) calculations from in-situ sensors (point measurements).
- Drought data from Copernicus Drought Observatory (raster format).
- Historical climate data from ECMWF ERA5-Land dataset (raster format).
- Real time weather data from open meteo providers (raster format).
- LPIS data for extrapolation of existing in-situ data to regional level.

External Knowledge:

- Typical values of irrigation needs per crop type in the region.
- Historical values of irrigation needs per crop type in the region.

The resulting user story

By combining farm-level irrigation data (FMIS) with ERA5 historical climate records, real-time meteorological inputs, and Copernicus drought indicators, CAP authorities can monitor water usage at multiple scales. **This integration enables calculation of crop water demand and water productivity indicators, development of seasonal and monthly irrigation models** using ET_0 , identification of extreme events that justify deviations from sustainability goals and support for regional irrigation strategies during droughts, ensuring efficient water allocation.

The resulting user story could be: *As a CAP policymaker I would like to estimate/calculate irrigation water needs in NUTS3 xyz area for 2023.*

The resulting system strengthens compliance with CAP indicators (R.22: sustainable water use: share of irrigated land under commitments; R.23PR: sustainable water use share of utilised agricultural area under supported commitments to improve water balance; or I.17: reducing pressure on water source), supports GAEC 4 conditionality, aligns with the [Water Framework Directive](#), and contributes to [United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 6.4.2](#) on water efficiency. Ultimately, it **enhances climate resilience and promotes sustainable agricultural practices** across Europe.

Giorgos Charvalis presented the [lessons learned from the application of the irrigation and water management user story through the Policy Monitoring Tool \(PMT\)](#). The case study confirmed that the PMT is adaptable, capable of generating meaningful outputs from both open and in-situ datasets. This adaptability underscored its relevance for agricultural insurance and climate-risk assessment, aligning closely with the objectives of ELGA, the Hellenic Agricultural Insurance Organisation.

The findings demonstrated how **regional metrics such as irrigation practices, pesticide use, and yields can complement CAP result and output indicators**, thereby confirming the tool's flexibility to integrate Earth Observation, farm-level, and open data for regional policy insights. The exercise showed the **potential for replication and customisation across different regions**, while presenting the added value of such tools for insurance and risk management tasks beyond traditional CAP monitoring. Important to note that the case study emphasised the **need for diversified stakeholder engagement** and iterative feedback loops and suggested

Step-by-step flow of the UML Sequence Diagram for the Greek irrigation and water management case study

pathways for interoperability with national databases and the automation of data pipelines.

At the same time, **different limitations were identified**. During the process, the dissolution of the Greek Payment Authority of the Common Agricultural Policy generated institutional instability and weakened the depth of results. This also affected to data access as the **lack of complementary official datasets**, such as Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS), hindered policy level validation and raised uncertainties about scalability when datasets are incomplete. Lastly, highlighting that the tool was often perceived more as a feature provider than

as a systemic monitoring solution, which limited its policy weight, and administrative burden and limited digital readiness discouraged formal collaboration, while the absence of official feedback reduced the weight of the outcomes.

These challenges underline the **importance of stable institutional frameworks, comprehensive data availability, and active stakeholder involvement** to ensure that monitoring tools such as the Policy Monitoring Tool can achieve their full potential in supporting CAP Strategic Plans and broader sustainability objectives.

Final conclusions and key takeaways

The module's work on technical protocols and methodological guidelines yielded several conclusions regarding the future of data integration and governance within the CAP framework:

- The data interoperability problem must be addressed through a combined approach that serves both the requirements of agri-food ICT solution providers and the specific needs of CAP monitoring and

implementation. For instance, the forthcoming "Common European Agriculture Data Space" should be designed to be readily feasible for utilising and collecting essential farm-level data necessary for the successful implementation of the CAP.

- Multiple and parallel data standardisation mechanisms and semantics exist across the agriculture, environment, and food application domains and it is

recommended starting with straightforward standardisation efforts, such as establishing an EU-wide taxonomy for basic data structures (e.g., crop types, pests/diseases, units of measurement, and growth stages).

- The results derived from data sharing and interoperability programmes (such as H2020 and Horizon Europe) are not yet integrated, or only to a limited extent, with commercial agriculture ICT systems. This suggests that the outcomes are useful, but there is currently a **lack of significant obligations or clear benefits** compelling stakeholders to share this data. The future development of the Agri Data Space represents a vital step forward in addressing this gap.
- The interoperability mechanism can be successfully **applied as an enabler layer** on top of existing systems (such as IACS and FMISs). There is no necessity to fundamentally alter the internal operations of these established systems. This approach **minimises disruption** while maximising compatibility.

- The user-story methodology aids in the **effective linkage between high-level policy objectives and practical technical requirements**. This approach is instrumental in ensuring that the development of complex digital tools is directly aligned with the specific, goal-oriented needs of end-users, such as CAP Managing Authorities and Paying Agencies.

Workcloud summarising the session

Next steps

The Academy training session, concluded with a series of next steps, including that the meeting materials and the report on the main elements discussed will be available on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#).

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

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New training modules of the Academy will be published in the near future, [here](#).

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